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**INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN INVESTORS
IN THE STOCK MARKET: A STUDY WITH
REFEENCE TO MANGALURU**

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Introduction:

Investment means keeping some money aside so that it grows more valuable after a period of time. At the same time investing is difficult because people have to be patient and disciplined for long stretches of time. It's because all around us we see people spending and having the time of their lives while we sacrifice those pleasures. Investing involves lot of decisions - differentiating between needs and wants. Men and women differ in their approach to the investment game. Particularly stock market investment has become popular among men and women. In most of the cases the women want to earn stable income. While farming investment portfolio women are concerned about safety, liquidity and profitably but men mostly think about profitability alone. This study is an attempt to study the behavior pattern of women who invest in stock market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To study the investment behaviour of women in stock market in Mangaluru
- To find out the awareness level, frequency of investment and objectives behind investment.
- To find out whether the women investors are looking for long term growth or risk or return of liquidity and to analysis their long term financial goals.
- To study the various factors affecting financial behavior of women investor , to analyze how women handle financial task, risk and the influence of investment in social empowerment of women.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY**a) Primary Data**

Primary data has been used in this study. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire by conducting personal interviews with women who invest in stock market.

b) Secondary Data For this study secondary data was collected through various sources such as magazines, articles, news papers and business journals.

Literature Review

- V.A.AVADHANI, INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT He says investment is many things to many persons. If one person advanced some money to another, it may be his loan which may be considered his investment for a return. If another person has purchased one kg of gold for the purpose of price appreciation or a consumer durable like washing machine for the flow of service it is his investment. If he purchases an insurance plan or a pension plan it is an investment. Hence there is various types of investment for different persons. Investment activity includes buying and selling or trading in the claims on money or promissory notes. An investment for one may be disinvestment of another as in the case of stock market trading or may be a fresh investment in a new issue. Saving is abstaining from present consumption for a future use. Savings are sometimes autonomous coming from households as a matter of habit. But bulk of the savings come for specific objectives like interest income, future needs, contingencies, precautionary purposes, or growth in future wealth , leading to rise in the standard of living .
- M RANGANATHAN, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT, (2009) Investors' behavior deals with emotional reaction people experience after realizing they have made an error in judgment. It has faced with the prospect of selling a stock, investors become emotionally affected by the price at which they purchased the stock. They avoid selling it as a way to avoid the regret of having made a bad investment, as well as the embarrassment of reporting a loss JEROME BERNARD COHEM, EDWARD D ZINBERG, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT Conducted a very detailed research in gender differences on different types of investments. His results concluded that both genders tend to choose differently in types of investments. For example, men preferred mutual bonds more than women did. H also found that almost twice men than women chose health insurance. More men also chose life insurance, stock, shares and recurring deposits. However, the only type of investments chosen by more women was fixed deposits.
- SANDEEP SHANBHAG, IN THE WONDERLAND OF INVESTMENT, (2016-2017) The study was aimed to measure financial knowledge in investment decision making, which will be helpful in this study to measure the gender gap and concluded if financial literacy is really a factor which accounts for gender gap differences. The women tend to have relatively lower level of financial knowledge. Concluded that people must be “financially knowledgeable in order to make informed investment decisions and take advantages of investment opportunities.”
- CHANDRA P, INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AND PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT(2008).Investment behavior of rural investors in their study states that the investment culture among the people of a country is an essential prerequisite for capital formation and the faster growth of an economy. Investment culture refers to the attitude, perceptions and willingness of the individuals and institutions in placing their savings in various financial assets more popularly known as securities.

- SELLAPPAN BALASWAMY AND VANITHA SOMASUNDARAM, INVESTMENT BEHAVIOR OF EQUITY INVESTOR, (2013)
In their study, “Gender difference in risk behavior in financial decision making: An experimental investment strategies as men and women are motivated by different “needs”. They put forward the idea that these difference “needs” and therefore strategies, may be that women are looking more for security whereas men are looking for returns.

Data analysis

Table showing demographic profile of the respondents

occupation	No of respondents	PERCENTAGE
Government sector Employee	7	11.7%
Private sector Employee	18	30%
Self Employed	20	33.3%
Others(home makers and students)	15	25%
Age	No of respondents	PERCENTAGE
Between 20 and 30	24	40%
Between 30 and 40	18	30%
Between 40 and 50	10	16%
Above 50	8	14%
Marital status	No of Respondents	PERCENTAGE
Married	38	63.3%
Single	22	36.7%
Annual income	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than Rs100000	15	25%
Between Rs100000 and Rs250000	18	30%
Between Rs250000 and 500000	17	28.3%
Above 500000	10	16.7%

Interpretation:

- It can be seen that 33.33% of the respondents are self-employed,30% are private sector employees,12% are government employees, and the remaining 25% includes home makers, students etc., Here the trend of the women becoming financially independent is highlighted.
- Most of the women investors are in the age group between 20-30 years and the least number of investors are above 50 years of age, this may be because of lack of knowledge about investment among older generation.
- It can be observed that 63.30% of the respondents are married and the remaining 36.70% of the respondents are not married. Therefore it can be said that most of the married women have the tendency to invest in much secure investments which gives benefit in the long run and the rest of the respondents are said to be more risk averse when compared to married people.
- Majority of the women are earning an income which lies between Rs.100000 and Rs.250000, 28% of the respondents earn between Rs.250000 and Rs.500000, 25% of the respondents earn less than Rs.100000 and the remaining 17% earn more than 500000. These investors plan their investments in accordance with their earnings.

Table showing investment pattern of women investor

Income invested	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than 10%	36	30%
10% to 20%	52	43.3%
20% to 30%	28	23.4%
More than 30%	4	3.3%
Preferred investment	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Equity shares	74	61.67%
Preference shares	24	20%
Debentures	22	18.33%
Type of investor	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Diversified investor	92	76.67%
Unvaried investor	28	23.33%

Frequency of investment	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Weekly	4	3.33%
Monthly	42	35%
Quarterly	28	23%
Half yearly	24	20%
Yearly	22	18.33%
Rate of return	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
6% to 8%	22	18.33%
8% to 10%	46	38.33%
10% to 12%	36	30%
More than 12%	16	13.4% %
Behavioral pattern	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Risk Seeker	36	30%
Risk Averse	30	25%
Risk Neutral	54	45%
Factors considered while investing	No of Respondents	PERCENTAGE
long term growth	10	8%
Risk	36	30%
Return	50	42%
Retirement Income	4	3%
Liquidity	20	17.00%

Interpretation:

- Majority of the women have invested 10% to 20% of their income making them conservative investors. 30% of them have invested less than 10% of their income,

23.40% of them have invested 20% to 30% of their income. The remaining 3.30% of the respondents have invested more than 30% of their income as they have thorough knowledge of all the investment avenues and are willing to take more risks.

- 62% of the investors invest in equity shares and gain ownership rights of that company. 20% of the investors invest in preference shares and they receive dividend payments before equity share holders. 18% of the respondents invests in debentures and are free to exchange debentures for company stocks if given the option to.
- It can be seen that majority of the investors invest in the company with higher capital gain than the company with high dividend policy this may be because high dividend yield doesn't always mean that a stock is a good choice, there are times when a high dividend yield means the company might not have future investment project.
- 77% of the investors prefer to diversify their investment in order to reduce the risk, whereas 23% of the investors prefer to invest in the same securities as they do not want to involve any change in their investment pattern.
- It shows that 3.33% of the investors invest weekly, 18.33% invest yearly, 20% invest half yearly, 23% invest quarterly and majority of the investors invest monthly which helps them to stay focused on their long-term goals.
- Majority of investors expect to achieve a return of 8 to 12% on their investment. An investor typically sets the required rate of return by adding a risk premium to the interest percentage that could be gained by investing excess funds in a risk-free investment, 30% of women expect a return of 10 to 12%, 18.33% expect a return of 6 to 8% and 13.4% expects a return more than 12% on their investment.
- Majority of 45% of the investors are risk neutral where the investor places himself in the middle of the risk spectrum, represented by risk seeking investors at one end and risk averse investors at the other end. Whereas 30% of the investors are risk seekers and 25% of the investors are risk averse.

Findings

- Majority of the women are willing to take some risk to get overall high returns, few of the women prefer investing in safer investments and very less percentage of women are not concerned about short term decrease in their investment for high, long term returns.
- Majority of investors depend upon the financial advisors while investing due to lack of confidence or lack of knowledge about investment. 23% of investor depend on the brokers, 22% of investors take decisions on their own based on their knowledge, experience and awareness level.
- Majority of investors are satisfied with the diversification of assets and dividend they receive, dissatisfied with the quick plan, highly satisfied with safety and tax benefit they get from their investments

SUGGESTIONS

- Women should be encouraged to invest in more avenues and participate in the investment avenues which involve high risks and also high returns.

- Women should increase their awareness level of the portfolio diversification to spread their risk.
- Women should recognize their financial independence and plan for the future to make it better.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that generally, women are conservative investors and they feel that safeguarding what they have as their top priority. These investors want to avoid risk particularly the risk of losing any principal that is their original investment even if that means they will have to settle for very modest returns. They prefer investing in equity shares when compared with other stock market avenues.